

REVIEW OF THE THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE NEED FOR LOGISTICS DEVELOPMENT IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. *Logistics systems serve as the foundation of infrastructure support for interaction between economic entities at the national and regional levels, creating the necessary conditions for economic development and enhancing the well-being of the population. This article addresses the issues of logistics, sales, and delivery of agricultural products, as well as agricultural processing, and the environmental and conservation impact of food production on nature. As well as monitoring and logistics systems for fresh agricultural products, which face technological challenges including: product labeling and identification, process monitoring, information systems for supply chains “from farm to fork”.*

Keywords: *logistics, agriculture, economy, distance, production, transportation, sales, storage, fruit and vegetables.*

Introduction. In the market economy of the transitional period, it is crucial to focus on developing the trade and logistics sector while implementing evidence-based market mechanisms. This objective must be addressed comprehensively through entrepreneurial and commercial activities – an indispensable component of market systems. The fundamental challenge of establishing reliable food security for the population remains unresolved. Economically, the country has lost its former product distribution system without fully replacing it with market-driven alternatives. Unlike developed nations, Uzbekistan lacks a systematically organized food distribution framework. This situation is exacerbated by the absence of state support mechanisms for domestic producers, who are essential for supplying wholesale markets.[1]

Changes occurring in the commodity and material sphere and trade, caused by the transformation in the market economy, fill economic (commercial) activity with new content. The formation of various forms of ownership, expansion of production, consumer demand, growing competition, and sustainable business management predetermine increasing requirements for the organization and management of trade. First of all, this concerns the wholesale market, which should become the leading link in the emerging food distribution system. In particular, the role of logistics in modern, in particular, domestic agribusiness, first of all, it is necessary to emphasize its integral and optimization nature. The use of logistics concepts and systems allows optimizing the material, financial, labor, and other resources of agro-industrial organizations associated with the management of their flows. [1]

Methodology. The agricultural sector is the backbone of many economies, providing food and raw materials for industry. However, the sector often faces logistical and supply problems. Food security is a critical issue for reducing hunger and increasing food security. While the goal is to increase production, minimizing losses in the food supply chain has been largely ignored until recently. Inefficient logistics can lead to increased costs, production delays, and even spoilage.[3]

Current transformations in global and domestic supply chain systems, driven by intensifying competition and rising costs in production and distribution processes, are prompting

manufacturers, wholesale sellers, and wholesale buyers to consolidate efforts in managing goods flows and associated information and financial streams. International practice confirms the advantages and efficiency of large-scale wholesale entities. Potent independent wholesale structures of various types can significantly improve the economic position of partnered retail and small-scale wholesale businesses through:

- Strategic pricing policies;
- Centralization of substantial inventory shares,
- Organized regular deliveries in economically viable batches,
- Eliminating the need for small wholesalers and retailers to maintain large warehouse spaces or pay rent;
- Thereby minimizing fixed capital investments;
- Reducing property taxes;
- Implementing efficient supply chain schemes via modern logistics solutions.

Global practice has repeatedly proven the effectiveness of logistics integration, expanded the theoretical and applied tools, and ensured the leading positions of market players. The theoretical and methodological foundations of logistics tools and the very definition of the term “logistics” have a significant interdisciplinary nature and are rooted in economic theory, planning and forecasting, mathematics, and material and technical supply. [4]

Optimization of logistics processes in Uzbekistan's economic complex is a key factor in the country's socio-economic development in the era of digitalization, which is characterized by market liberalization and increased external influence. To accelerate the country's economic development, it is necessary to promptly introduce effective technologies that contribute to achieving a regime of maximum self-sufficiency, replacing imported goods, and stimulating inter-industry links in the reproduction and modernization of the national economy.

Discussion and analysis. Logistics management is currently crucial for the agricultural sector. The key determining factors for the efficiency of where an agrarian producer can transport their products are as follows [2]:

- the distance between the location of the agricultural producer and the market (transportation distance), which is measured in kilometers or other conventional units of distance depending on whether long or short distances are implied.
- travel time, which depends on many factors: weather conditions, vehicle load capacity, and availability of roads (in other words, the number of hours of travel per day).
- cost per kilogram transported by land compared to air or sea freight. Air freight costs can be three times lower than road freight, even if it takes longer.

The theoretical and methodological foundations of logistics management, while simultaneously serving as the final link in the supply chain, cannot be limited exclusively to the managerial context. Yet, possessing a formalized structure and high adaptability, logistics—in its contemporary interpretation—synthesizes the management of costs, inventories, investments, supply, production, distribution, and reverse logistics techniques. Many companies that do not have their own assets and resort to logistics outsourcing services do not see the need to organize their complexity. In practice, national logistics providers often lack the capabilities for wide territorial coverage, building an effective supply chain, financial assets, and transport and warehouse capacity. There are not enough resources, and then the logistics companies themselves, the logistics service providers, turn to third-party organizations that provide a certain function (transportation, warehouses, recycling, etc.). The greatest effect can be achieved by integrating the

interests of producers, the final link, and formally all parties involved, using adaptive intelligent and analytical systems of logistics management. Let us present a classification of risks characteristic of logistics distribution systems (Table 1) [3]

Table 1 – Classification of risks in logistics distribution systems. [3]

Functional area	Exogenous risks	Endogenous risks	Data risks, external and internal environment
Production	Production disruption due to a lack of materials and components production capacities	Disruption of production due to malfunction of capacities, reduction of production capabilities	Disruption of the software, information systems of both the manufacturer and the supplier of materials and components
Transportation	Global change in external conditions for the functioning of supply chains	Disruption of deliveries as a result of the failure to receive goods consignments, lack of transport vehicles, loss of cargo as a result of theft, environmental risks	Change in delivery dates, temporary discrepancy in cargo tracking due to failure in the information system ensuring transportation processes
Storage	Loss of goods due to natural disasters, emergencies	Damage or loss of goods during storage due to failure to comply with proper conditions	Change in delivery dates due to loss of goods or a change in their quality, failures in the information system for processing orders
Sales	Fall or bifurcational growth of purchasing power due to global reasons	Loss of qualitative and quantitative indicators of products, resulting in a drop in the competitiveness of the product, excessive freezing of stocks, damages caused by the disruption of deliveries, and increased delivery times	Software failure, order management system

The consequences of the crisis generated by regional strife and conflicts, initially negative, but stimulating the growth of logistics activities, determined the strategic directions for the development of agricultural logistics in Uzbekistan.

In order to characterize their role and significance in the process of accelerated development of the agro-industrial complex, it is necessary to determine short-term and strategic measures that are necessary to ensure stable development and applied efficiency of the country's logistics in the long term.

In updating the significant positive results of agricultural activities in the area of development of production and marketing specialization and logistics support, it is necessary to note several complex issues that exist in the work of distribution systems and are directly aggravated about the agricultural specialization of the district. [6]

Initially, it should be emphasized that every year the volumes of material and accompanying information, financial, and service flows are increasing, which have not only an interregional but also an export focus. In the context of temporary complications in the market field associated with the strengthening of sanctions restrictions, problematic elements that complicate the movement of flow processes in the district economy must be investigated and analyzed promptly. [7]

The main dominant reasons that complicate the situation in the logistics support of commodity and transport flows are the following:

1. Global annual growth and complexity of logistics systems, justified by the growing demand of the economy and population, sometimes leading to a dissonant reaction of the existing infrastructure.

2. The unbalanced development of trade and transport infrastructure in the region, driven primarily by global sporting and other major international events. Regarding the hosting of the aforementioned events, a sound government policy should be acknowledged; however, there is also a noted lack of commercial sector interest and its minimal involvement in developing the region's infrastructure.

3. Insufficient use of the advantages of transit importance in the global logistics services market.

4. Often, the level of logistical support for flow processes in the regional goods distribution system is not high enough.

5. Insufficient efficiency of investment processes in the development of logistics infrastructure, again due to the lack of interest of the commercial sector in innovative reproduction.

6. Growing imbalance between increasing demand for logistics services and the load on infrastructure capacity.

7. In our opinion, purely agricultural problems may include issues of high-quality storage of products in the region under study or, as one of the possible options, prospects for accelerated transfer and transportation of products to other regions.

Examining the agrarian specialization and logistical infrastructure of the country, we note a growing demand for logistics services.

From a theoretical and methodological perspective, this situation requires instrumental support in the form of forecast models for the regional development of the southern regions. These models have been formulated for accelerated strategic development, with a focus on interregional cooperation and strengthening the role of export capacity.

Table-2. Development of agriculture, forestry, and fisheries in the country's gross domestic product. [8]

A significant increase in the volume of production of agricultural products in Uzbekistan as a whole, for example, the development of agriculture, forestry, and fisheries in the country's gross domestic product for January-September 2023 amounted to 750.9 trillion soums, an increase of 105.8% compared to the same period in 2022. The gross domestic product was equivalent to 65.0 billion US dollars. The gross added value of agriculture, forestry, and fisheries amounted to 168.2 trillion soums, or 14.6 billion US dollars. The share of added value in the gross domestic product was 23.7%.

In Uzbekistan, the agricultural specialization of regions with significant resource, natural and climatic resources suitable for the development of agricultural production continues to grow. In general, it demonstrates positive dynamics and, regardless of the difficult economic situation associated with liberalization, high inflation rates, and global instability, the agro-industrial complex of Uzbekistan is trying to strengthen its position both in providing the domestic market and in achieving a stable and annual increase in the share of exports.

In the first 9 months of 2023, 7.0 million tons of grain were grown (103.3% more than in the same period last year), 8.1 million tons (101.5%) of vegetables, and 2.7 million tons (101.1%) of potatoes. In terms of regions, the volume of grain production in the Fergana region amounted to 780.1 thousand tons, in the Kashkadarya region - 775.6 thousand tons, in the Surkhandarya region - 694.2 thousand tons, the volume of vegetable production in the Andijan region amounted to 1295.5 thousand tons, in the Samarkand region – 1240.4 thousand tons, in the Surkhandarya region – 884.6 thousand tons, the volume of potato production in the Samarkand region amounted to 549.4 thousand tons, Tashkent region – 303.3 thousand tons, Surkhandarya region – 301.6 thousand tons. In addition, in 2023, 2.3 million tons (103.1% more than the same period last year) of fruits, 1.6 million tons (103.4%) of melons and gourds, and 1.3 million tons (93.2%) of grapes were produced. In terms of regions, the volume of fruit production in the Andijan region was 475.8 thousand tons, in the Fergana region 314.5 thousand tons, in the Samarkand region 297.9 thousand tons, the volume of production of melons and gourds amounted to 219.2 thousand tons in the Surkhandarya region, 198.4 thousand tons in the Jizzakh region, 192.9 thousand tons in the Syrdarya region, the volume of production of grapes amounted to 494.0 thousand tons in the Samarkand region, 175.2 thousand tons in the Bukhara region, 114.6 thousand tons in the Fergana region.

Table-3. Dynamics of agricultural production volumes in January-September 2023. [12]

The theoretical foundations of integrative logistics management—governing distribution processes, shaping quality characteristics, and determining final prices—remain crucial variables that define the competitiveness of goods and services, as well as the quality of market advantage growth. This growth depends on market conditions and the precision in fulfilling delivery obligations. Moreover, when organizing distribution systems for agricultural products—characterized by high demand and conditionally limited shelf life—emphasis must be placed precisely on structuring logistics processes. The regional agro-industrial distribution system itself must meet the requirements of integrated logistics services for managing flow processes and minimizing disruptions in operational stability.[9]

Conclusion. Thus, expedited development of distribution systems can be achieved within the alternatives offered by the market. This algorithm involves several managerial blocks, including control, management, and monitoring as core logistics activities. These activities optimize the integrative functions of the distribution system under consideration.

In the context of modern conditions, the improvement of logistics processes, the increase in agricultural exports, and the functioning of the country's agro-industrial sector necessitate solving a complex set of tasks: finding compromises for all market participants (primarily economic feasibility), utilizing transport and warehouse technologies, among others. Specifically, addressing the following problems will enable the development of this sector:

- The need to study the interaction between logistics systems in urban and agricultural sectors;
- Applying an evolutionary logistics approach, implying an integration process of agrologistics and urban logistics;
- Implementing coordinated distribution systems functioning as collection hubs, etc.

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